

SOCIO-ECONOMIC DETERMINANTS AND THE MANIFESTATIONS OF ABUSE AMONG STREET CHILDREN IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

Street children in Nigeria face persistent abuse and multidimensional vulnerabilities due to entrenched socio-economic hardships, family breakdowns and weak protective institutions. Yet, these challenges remain inadequately addressed in policy and academic discourse. This study examined the socio-economic conditions, manifestations and multidimensional implications of abuse experienced by street children in Nigeria, with a particular focus on the structural and systemic factors that heighten their vulnerability. Guided by the Child Protection Theory of Change developed by Philip Cook, Michael Wessells, and Michele Cook, the research employed a qualitative method, relying on secondary data sourced from scholarly literature, institutional reports, and empirical case studies across Nigerian urban centres. Thematic content analysis was employed to identify patterns of abuse and their broader effects on the lives of street children. Findings revealed that household poverty, parental unemployment, family disintegration, harmful cultural practices such as witchcraft labelling, and institutional neglect are significant drivers of child vulnerability and street migration. The manifestations of abuse, ranging from physical and sexual violence to emotional trauma, economic exploitation and social exclusion, have severe social, psychological and developmental consequences. These include poor mental health, disrupted education, stunted growth, moral disorientation and chronic marginalisation. The study underscores the critical need for stronger child protection frameworks, inclusive social policies and targeted interventions that address both the root causes and outcomes of street children. By providing a theoretically informed and evidence-based analysis, this research contributes to the growing body of knowledge on child rights violations and offers practical insights for policymakers, social workers and child advocacy organisations in Nigeria.

Keywords: *Socio-Economic Determinants, Manifestations of Abuse, Implications, Street Children*

Introduction

The phenomenon of street children has become a visible and troubling manifestation

of child abuse and systemic neglect in many parts of the world, particularly in developing countries such as Nigeria. These children, often found living or working on the streets without parental care or adult supervision, represent a significant population of vulnerable minors exposed to various forms of abuse, exploitation and deprivation. Scholars such as Asangausung (2024), Alawiye-Adams and Babatunde (2013), Fantahun and Taa (2022) and Mboho and Udo (2018) have noted that the rising prevalence of street children is largely driven by socio-economic challenges such as poverty, unemployment, rapid urbanisation, family breakdown and harmful cultural practices. Many children end up on the streets not by choice but due to systemic failures within their families and the wider society. In some cases, children are expelled from their homes based on accusations of witchcraft or as a result of parental death, neglect, or abandonment (Chineyemba, 2019; Asangausung *et al.*, 2025). These children are frequently denied access to education, healthcare and protection, thereby increasing their susceptibility to abuse.

Street life, which encompasses homelessness, informal work and marginal social existence, has become a survival strategy for many of these children. They engage in various activities such as hawking, begging, or scavenging and often face violence, exploitation and social exclusion in the process. As Karlson (2015) observes, street life is not only an economic condition but a reflection of systemic exclusion. In Lagos State, Akwa Ibom State, Abia State, Rivers State, Cross River State and others, the sight of children engaged in street hawking and menial labour is common. These children, often from impoverished or dysfunctional homes, contribute to household income by selling goods or offering services on busy streets, sometimes during school hours. Such circumstances not only disrupt their education but also expose them to significant risks including physical harm, sexual abuse, emotional trauma and developmental stagnation (Atumba *et al.*, 2023; Brown *et al.*, 2012; Wafula & Edema, 2023).

Despite legal provisions such as the Child Rights Act (LFN, 2003), which aims to protect the rights and welfare of children, the growing number of children on the streets raises critical questions about the efficacy of these interventions. The absence of accurate data on the number of street children in several states in Nigeria, including Akwa Ibom State further complicates policy responses and resource allocation by government agencies and non-governmental organisations (Ukpong, 2021). The existing literature, while rich in discussions on child abuse and streetism in Nigeria (Atumba *et al.*, 2023; Ogan and Ogan, 2021; Mboho & Ndaeyo, 2019), has not paid sufficient attention to the socio-economic conditions, manifestations and the social, psychological and developmental implications of abuse on street children in Nigeria. This represents a significant gap that this study sought to address.

Against this backdrop, this study examined the socio-economic conditions that predispose children to street life, the manifestations of abuse they experience and assessing the broader social, psychological and developmental implications of such abuse. By situating the experiences of street children within the socio-cultural and economic context of Nigeria, the study aimed to contribute meaningfully to the academic discourse on child vulnerability, inform policy interventions and advocate for a more robust and responsive child protection framework.

Research Objectives

The main aim of this study was to examine to the socio-economic conditions, manifestations and the social, psychological and developmental implications of abuse on

street children in Nigeria. Specific objectives were to:

- i. investigate the socio-economic conditions that contribute to the abuse and vulnerability of street children in Nigeria.
- ii. examine the manifestations of abuse experienced by street children in Nigeria.
- iii. assess the social, psychological and developmental implications of abuse on street children in Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

- i. What socio-economic conditions contribute to the abuse and vulnerability of street children in Nigeria?
- ii. What are the manifestations of abuse experienced by street children in Nigeria?
- iii. What are the social, psychological and developmental implications of abuse on street children in Nigeria?

Conceptualisation

Street Children

According to Mokafane (2014), there is no universal definition of street children. Sometimes the terms used for street children differ depending on the region of the country. In North America and Western Europe, street children are referred to as “homeless children” interchangeably with “street children”, while in countries in Africa, Asia, Eastern Europe and Latin America, they are referred to as “street children” (Mokafane, 2014). According to Ibrahim (2012), there are many definitions of street children, but the definitions include the following most important parameters: “Any girl or boy ... for whom the street (in the widest sense of the word, including unoccupied dwellings, wasteland, etc.) has become his or her habitual abode and/or source of livelihood; and who is inadequately protected, supervised, or directed by responsible adults” (UNCHS, 2000:73).

Ezeokana *et al.* (2014) identified four categories for street children: (a) Children who work and return to their families at night. They are likely to attend school. (b) Independent street workers. Among this category of street children, family relationships begin to deteriorate, their education declines and delinquency increases. (c) Children of street families who work and live on the streets with their families. (d) Children who have broken contact with their families, who reside in the street full-time. Ibrahim (2012) also stated that there are two groups of street children. The two groups of street children were: (a) children of the street (refers to homeless children and the streets of cities are their source of livelihood, where they sleep and live) and (b) children on the street (working and living on the streets during the day and return to their homes at night). However, there is no clear distinction between these two groups as their definitions often differ; some 'children of the street' may still have links with their families, and some 'children on the street' may sleep on the streets (UNICEF, 2001).

Similarly, Ezeokana *et al.* (2014) conceptualised street children into three categories in terms of family contact. These categories were as follows: (a) Children on the street are children who hawk goods and other merchandise on the streets but are always with their families. Most in this category attend school and return home at the end of the day. (b) Children of the street (living and working on the street). This category views the street as their home, and because that is where they find money, food, shelter and companions among peers. For this group, family ties may exist, but are perceived negatively. Visits to their homes are

not regular, and frequently they may experience parental rejection and physical abuse. (c) Children who are completely abandoned and neglected. For this group, family ties with the biological family are lost, and they are completely on their own materially and psychologically.

In summary, street children are minors who live and work on the streets, often without stable shelter or consistent care from a family or guardian. The concept of street children highlights a vulnerable group facing numerous challenges due to socioeconomic factors, family dynamics and urbanisation. Categories of street children include:

- i. Children of the Street: Those who live full-time on the streets with no significant family ties.
- ii. Children on the Street: Those who work or spend a significant amount of time on the streets but return home regularly.
- iii. Street-Family Children: Those who live on the streets with their family.

Many street children are homeless, sleeping in public spaces like parks, alleys, or abandoned buildings. They engage in various activities to survive, such as begging, street vending, scavenging, or performing small jobs. Economic hardship is a primary driver, pushing children to the streets to support themselves or their families. Parental joblessness often forces children into street work. Abuse and neglect at home lead many children to flee. The loss of a caregiver can leave children without support. Families migrating to cities in search of better opportunities may end up living in slums, where children end up on the streets. Street children often engage in hazardous work. They are vulnerable to physical, emotional and sexual abuse and trafficking. Many street children do not attend school, limiting their future opportunities and perpetuating poverty. Exposure to harsh weather, malnutrition and lack of healthcare leads to various health issues. Street life causes significant emotional and psychological stress (Asangausung, 2024).

Child Abuse

Fayaz and Khurshid (2020), Fayaz (2019) and Mboho and Ndaeyo (2019) define child abuse as any action, behaviour, or gesture of another person, an adult, or a child, that seriously harms the child. It can be physical, sexual or emotional, but often it can also be a lack of love, care and attention. Similarly, WHO (2002) notes that it includes any form of physical or emotional abuse that harms the child's life. It could be sexual violence, neglect or abandonment, or after commercial or other forms of exploitation.

Literature Review

Socio-Economic Conditions that Contribute to the Abuse and Vulnerability of Street Children

The socio-economic conditions contributing to the abuse and vulnerability of street children in Nigeria and beyond are complex, multifaceted and deeply rooted in structural inequalities. Across studies, poverty, social disintegration and harmful cultural beliefs emerge as key drivers pushing children into precarious street life. Fantahun and Taa (2022) illustrate that street children in Gondar City, Ethiopia, are often victims of social exclusion, driven by the absence of parental figures, pervasive poverty and societal stigma. The resulting deprivation of basic needs and emotional support exacerbates their marginalisation, effectively excluding them from access to the rights and resources enjoyed by other children.

This exclusion is compounded by systemic neglect and daily exposure to abuse, as

highlighted by Chimdessa and Cheire (2018), who document the routine experiences of physical, sexual and emotional violence endured by street children in Addis Ababa. Their findings reveal that many of these children were displaced by the death of parents or dysfunctional family relationships and found themselves navigating life on the streets in environments devoid of safety, stability, or social acceptance. The absence of formal protection mechanisms leads to their engagement in survival-based behaviours such as transactional sex and substance abuse, creating a cycle of exploitation and psychological deterioration.

In the Nigerian context, particularly in Akwa Ibom State, localised studies have expanded this understanding by drawing attention to cultural beliefs and family-based vulnerabilities. Stephen and Udisi (2016) found that accusations of witchcraft—often rooted in spiritual interpretations of misfortune—are a leading cause of child rejection and migration to the streets in the region. Such children are not only cast out but subjected to violence within their own homes and communities before ending up in hostile urban environments. The phenomenon of street children and their susceptibility to delinquent behaviour in Akwa Ibom State has been critically examined in several recent studies, with a particular focus on the socio-cultural and economic vulnerabilities that underpin their marginalisation. These studies—framed within relevant theoretical lenses—demonstrate how complex family dynamics and structural deprivation contribute to the emergence and persistence of child streetism and juvenile delinquency in the region.

Asangausung, Okorie and Ukommi (2025), drawing from Robert Agnew's General Strain Theory, provide empirical evidence linking parental poverty to the delinquent behaviours of street children. Conducted in Uyo, Eket and Ikot Ekpene, the study found that children forced into the streets due to economic hardship often lack access to fundamental necessities such as food, shelter and education. In such conditions, survival becomes the primary motivation for behaviour, pushing children into acts like theft, drug peddling and participation in gang activities. Poverty, in this context, is not just a condition but a criminogenic strain that fosters deviant adaptations in response to blocked legitimate opportunities.

In a related study, Asangausung, Okorie, Udousoro and Yagci (2025) examined the effects of parental wiccaphobia—irrational fear and belief in child witchcraft—on the life trajectories of street children. This study revealed how cultural stigma, particularly in spiritualised interpretations of misfortune, results in the rejection and abandonment of children accused of witchcraft. The emotional and physical displacement caused by such accusations strips children of familial protection and stability, increasing their exposure to street hazards and heightening their vulnerability to criminal influence. The trauma and marginalisation these children face in the aftermath of expulsion from their homes create a sustained cycle of vulnerability and behavioural maladjustment.

Complementing these findings, Asangausung, Okorie and Udom (2025), employing the Frustration-Aggression Theory, explored how unresolved paternity disputes contribute to streetism and delinquency among children in the same study locations. The study highlights that conflicts over paternal identity frequently result in child rejection, neglect and in extreme cases, expulsion from the home. Children affected by paternity disputes often experience psychological distress, social stigma and homelessness—conditions that significantly increase the likelihood of antisocial behaviours and criminal involvement as a means of asserting identity or securing basic survival.

Similarly, Hassen and Manus (2018) report on the socio-economic realities of street children in Shashemene Town, Ethiopia, noting that many come from households plagued by poverty and family breakdowns. These children often resort to unskilled street-based labour such as vending, shoe-shining and lottery selling to survive, while simultaneously facing persistent verbal, physical and sexual abuse. This aligns with findings in Akwa Ibom State, where the lack of structured family support, compounded by culturally sanctioned neglect, contributes to street children's heightened exposure to abuse and vulnerability.

Together, these studies demonstrate that the abuse and vulnerability of street children are not merely products of individual failings but symptoms of deeper socio-economic crises, including entrenched poverty, familial dysfunction, inadequate child protection systems and cultural practices that legitimise exclusion and violence. The cumulative effects of these factors deprive children of safety, dignity and developmental opportunities, while reinforcing cycles of marginalisation and intergenerational poverty. Therefore, addressing these root causes requires both targeted policy intervention and a broader socio-cultural transformation.

Manifestations of Abuse Experienced by Street Children

The literature on child abuse and street life in Nigeria, particularly within Akwa Ibom State and its surrounding regions, reveals a deeply entrenched socio-economic crisis that underpins the widespread phenomenon of child street hawking, neglect and abandonment. Child street hawking, identified as a prevalent form of child labour, contravenes the International Convention on the Rights of the Child by depriving minors of education, safety and proper childhood development (Mboho, 2020; Adedayo *et al.*, 2021). Empirical studies consistently link this practice to poverty, family disintegration and limited access to education (Ngozi *et al.*, 2024; Johnson & Ihesie, 2015). The economic hardship faced by families compels many children to engage in hazardous street trading to supplement household income, often exposing them to physical harm, exploitation and emotional distress (Adedayo, 2021; Magaji & Sarka, 2020).

Street children are routinely subjected to multiple and overlapping forms of abuse—physical, emotional, sexual and economic. Physical abuse is perpetrated by both peers and adults, including law enforcement officials, while emotional abuse manifests through verbal humiliation and systemic neglect. Sexual abuse, especially among girls, remains prevalent due to their lack of protection, with many coerced into exploitative relationships or transactional sex for survival (Fayaz & Khurshid, 2020). Neglect, often arising from parental absence, illness, or death, is a recurring theme in the narratives of street children, leaving them without access to basic services such as food, shelter and healthcare (Marici *et al.*, 2023). Psychological trauma, substance abuse and involvement in criminal activities are frequently reported as both outcomes and coping mechanisms associated with street life (Ojo, 2013; Peters *et al.*, 2023).

Studies across different Nigerian states (for example, Kogi, Taraba, Cross River) further illuminate how cultural practices, poor parenting and state-level inaction exacerbate the problem. Child abandonment, often driven by economic pressure, domestic violence, or harmful beliefs, leads to social exclusion and emotional instability, worsening the prospects of integration and development (Alaye, 2021; Atumba *et al.*, 2023). The cumulative effect of these abuses severely undermines children's physical health, mental stability, moral development and educational attainment, thus perpetuating intergenerational cycles of

poverty and marginalisation. The reviewed literature underscores the need for a multidimensional approach combining legal enforcement, poverty alleviation, access to education and psychosocial rehabilitation to protect street children and address the structural conditions enabling their exploitation.

Implications of Abuse on Street Children

The implications of abuse on street children are multidimensional, encompassing physical, psychological and behavioural consequences that impair their overall well-being and development. Literature across local and international contexts consistently portrays street children as a uniquely vulnerable population exposed to intersecting forms of harm. Obimakinde and Shabir (2023), in a qualitative study of street children in Ibadan, Nigeria, revealed how exposure to inadequate nutrition, open defecation, untreated infections and frequent road traffic accidents combine with verbal, sexual and substance abuse to produce cumulative health risks. Their findings illustrate the precarious balance street children maintain between domestic neglect and street survival, leading to poor health-seeking behaviours and reliance on informal healthcare systems.

The abuse experienced by street children frequently translates into high levels of substance use as a coping mechanism, with significant implications for mental and emotional stability. Umoayara and Ekot (2022) and Ogunkan *et al.* (2023) found a high prevalence of alcohol, nicotine and cannabis use among street children, although factors such as age, gender, school attendance and family stability were found to moderate the likelihood of substance use. These findings resonate with Tyler and Melander's (2013) path analysis, which identified a strong relationship between early-life abuse, exposure to street victimisation and substance dependency, especially among young adults with a history of family drug problems or intimate partner violence.

Cumber and Tsoka-Gwegweni (2015), through a systematic review of street children's health profiles across Africa, underscored the widespread health vulnerabilities faced by this population. From growth disorders and mental health issues to the high incidence of infectious and sexually transmitted diseases, the study emphasises how homelessness, violence and risky behaviours perpetuate cycles of disease and early mortality. This is further supported by Singh (2016), who identified emotional distress responses—such as anxiety, denial, self-mutilation and dissociation—among homeless children in Tamil Nadu, noting their perception of law enforcement not as protectors, but as aggressors contributing to their trauma.

Collectively, these studies demonstrate that abuse against street children results in lasting consequences that manifest in physical illness, psychological distress, social withdrawal and dangerous coping behaviours. The literature confirms that these children occupy a liminal space, where the absence of stable family structures, institutional protection and community support leaves them at the mercy of structural violence and neglect. The implications are not only personal but societal, as the unresolved trauma and developmental disruptions experienced by street children often feed into broader issues of public health insecurity, intergenerational poverty and youth marginalisation.

Theoretical Framework

The Child Protection Theory of Change, developed by Philip Cook, Michael Wessells and Michele Cook in 2014, offers a valuable conceptual lens for interpreting the

dynamics of abuse among street children in Nigeria. At its core, this theory emphasises a systems-oriented, contextually grounded and community-driven approach to addressing child vulnerability. It recognises that effective child protection requires both the reduction of risk factors and the strengthening of protective mechanisms within a child's environment. This aligns closely with the purpose of this study, which examines the socio-economic conditions, the manifestations of abuse and the social, psychological and developmental implications of such abuse on street children in Nigeria.

Applying the theory to the study's first objective, the socio-economic conditions contributing to the abuse and vulnerability of street children reflect systemic failures in protection. Issues such as poverty, parental unemployment, family breakdown and weak access to education constitute a fragile protective environment, leaving children exposed to neglect and exploitation. The theory asserts that when basic social support systems—family, community and state institutions—fail, the risk to children escalates significantly. In Nigeria, these socio-economic determinants push children into the streets, where they become susceptible to multiple forms of abuse, highlighting the absence of robust social safety nets and effective protective structures.

Concerning the second objective, which seeks to explore the manifestations of abuse, the theory provides a framework for understanding how various forms of violence—physical, sexual, psychological, economic and institutional—are symptomatic of deeper structural and normative breakdowns. It contends that where legal protections are poorly enforced and social norms tolerate or perpetuate child mistreatment, abuse becomes systemic and normalised. The Nigerian context illustrates this clearly through the widespread maltreatment of street children by law enforcement, the social acceptance of witchcraft accusations and institutional indifference. Such patterns of abuse underscore the urgent need for comprehensive legal reform, stronger social accountability and culturally informed behavioural change, all of which are central to the Theory of Change.

In addressing the third objective—examining the social, psychological and developmental implications of abuse—the theory's emphasis on child well-being and resilience becomes particularly relevant. Abuse experienced by street children often results in trauma, loss of self-worth, emotional instability and developmental delays. These outcomes reflect the breakdown of not just the external environment but also the child's internal coping systems. The theory highlights the importance of psychosocial recovery, reintegration into education and the re-establishment of supportive relationships as crucial to reversing the long-term impacts of abuse. Moreover, the framework encourages active child participation in protection strategies, affirming the agency of children as not only victims but also stakeholders in their own development.

By applying the Child Protection Theory of Change to this study, a clearer picture emerges of how systemic poverty, cultural practices and institutional neglect contribute to the vulnerability of street children, how abuse is perpetuated within this context and what long-term effects this has on their well-being. The theory thus strengthens the study's contribution to academic discourse and policy reform by offering a holistic, multi-layered understanding of child abuse that goes beyond immediate symptoms and addresses root causes and sustainable solutions.

Materials and Methods

This study employed a qualitative research method, which is well-suited for exploring the intricate and context-dependent realities surrounding the abuse and vulnerability of street children in Nigeria. The qualitative paradigm was selected to facilitate a rich, in-depth understanding of the lived experiences of these children and to uncover the socio-economic, psychological and developmental dimensions of abuse that may not be readily captured through quantitative methods.

The study adopted a descriptive qualitative survey design, which enabled a systematic investigation of the conditions, patterns and implications of abuse experienced by street children, as documented in existing scholarly and institutional sources. This design was appropriate given the study's aim to explore and describe the phenomena of streetism and child abuse without experimental manipulation, while allowing for interpretative depth and flexibility in capturing emerging themes across diverse contexts.

Data for this research were derived exclusively from secondary sources, including peer-reviewed journal articles, reports by international agencies such as UNICEF and WHO, empirical studies and institutional publications focused on street children in Nigeria and other parts of Sub-Saharan Africa. These materials were purposively selected based on their thematic relevance, methodological robustness and recency. The reliance on secondary data was also informed by ethical considerations related to working directly with vulnerable child populations, ensuring the research remained non-intrusive while still drawing from credible and comprehensive evidence.

The collected data were analysed using thematic content analysis, a method appropriate for identifying, analysing and interpreting recurrent patterns and themes within qualitative data. The analysis followed the framework proposed by Braun and Clarke (2006), which involves six phases: familiarisation with the data, generation of initial codes, searching for themes, reviewing themes, defining and naming themes and producing the final report. Thematic categories were developed in alignment with the study's objectives, focusing on three core areas: socio-economic conditions contributing to the abuse and vulnerability of street children, manifestations of abuse and the social, psychological and developmental consequences of such abuse.

To enhance the analytical rigour and theoretical coherence of the study, the Child Protection Theory of Change (Cook *et al.*, 2014) served as the guiding conceptual framework. This theory emphasises the interplay between structural, institutional and familial factors that either facilitate or inhibit effective child protection. By situating the findings within this theoretical framework, the study was able to conceptualise how systemic failures, social exclusion and inadequate policy implementation contribute to the cycle of abuse and marginalisation experienced by street children.

Overall, the methodological approach adopted in this study ensures a rigorous, ethically responsible and theoretically grounded exploration of child abuse within the context of streetism in Nigeria. It offers a robust analytical basis for understanding the multifaceted vulnerabilities of street children and provides insights that can inform evidence-based policy and intervention strategies.

Results and Discussions

What socio-economic conditions contribute to the abuse and vulnerability of street children in Nigeria?

Table 1: Socio-Economic Conditions Contributing to the Abuse and Vulnerability of

Street Children in Nigeria

Socio-Economic Condition	Description	Pathway to Abuse/Vulnerability	Supporting Evidence (Secondary Data)
Household Poverty	Low-income households are unable to meet basic needs such as food, shelter and education	Pushes children into street hawking, begging and exploitative labour, exposing them to physical and sexual abuse	Fantahun and Taa (2022); Adewumi and Bwowe (2024); Hassen and Manus (2018); Asangausung, Okorie and Ukommi (2025)
Parental Unemployment	Widespread joblessness, especially among male heads of households	Leads to neglect and abandonment; some children become breadwinners, increasing their exposure to exploitation	Adewumi and Bwowe (2024); Ayenew <i>et al.</i> (2020), Chimdessa and Cheire (2018); Hassen and Manus (2018)
Family Breakdown/Disintegration	Divorce, separation, domestic violence, or death of a parent	Reduces parental supervision and emotional support; increases risk of streetism and abuse by outsiders	Ayenew <i>et al.</i> (2020), Chimdessa and Cheire (2018); Hassen and Manus (2018); Tyler & Melander (2013); Asangausung, Okorie and Daniel (2025); Singh (2016)
Urban Migration and Homelessness	Rural-urban drift without sustainable livelihood plans	Results in slum dwelling or street life, increasing exposure to gang violence, trafficking and exploitation	Stephen and Udisi (2016)
Child Accusation of Witchcraft (Cultural Stigma)	Harmful belief systems attributing misfortune to child "witches"	Leads to rejection, torture and expulsion from the home, often followed by street dwelling and abuse	Asangausung (2024); Asangausung <i>et al.</i> (2024); Asangausung, Okorie, Udousoro and Yagci (2025); Stephen and Udisi (2016)
Inadequate Access to Education	Financial or social barriers preventing school attendance	Children stay idle or engage in labour; lack of education also limits their awareness of abuse and legal rights	Aransiola (2013)
Weak Institutional Protection	Ineffective child protection and enforcement of the Child Rights Act	Perpetuates abuse through underreporting, lack of justice and absence of rehabilitation programmes	Ifayomi <i>et al.</i> (2023); Singh (2016)

Source: Compiled by the Authors (2025)

The findings from the data revealed that the abuse and vulnerability of street children in Nigeria are deeply rooted in a combination of adverse socio-economic conditions that reinforce each other and perpetuate cycles of neglect, exploitation and marginalisation.

Central to this dynamic is household poverty, which undermines the ability of families to provide essential needs such as food, shelter, healthcare and education. In contexts where families are unable to meet these basic responsibilities, children are often compelled to seek means of survival through street hawking, begging, or engaging in informal labour. This exposes them to various forms of abuse, including physical violence, sexual exploitation and emotional trauma. This observation aligns with the findings of Hassen and Manus (2018) and Asangausung, Okorie and Ukommi (2025), who identify poverty as a driving force behind children's migration to the streets and their increased exposure to harm.

Parental unemployment further exacerbates this condition. When parents, particularly fathers, lack steady income, the stability of the family structure is compromised. Many children become economically active prematurely, taking on adult roles in hazardous environments. The psychological toll of such burden is significant, often manifesting as emotional neglect and behavioural problems. Chimdessa and Cheire (2018) observed that in urban centres like Addis Ababa, unemployment and economic strain were key factors that contributed to children being forced into transactional sex, drug use and other survival-based activities. In Nigeria, similar patterns are evident, as parental joblessness reduces adult supervision and forces children to fend for themselves in dangerous public spaces.

Family disintegration, whether through death, divorce, domestic violence, or abandonment, plays a critical role in weakening children's emotional and social foundations. The absence of a stable family unit creates a void in care and protection, which, in turn, facilitates the entry of children into street life. These children, lacking guardianship and emotional stability, are more vulnerable to recruitment into gangs, substance use and criminal activities. Singh (2016) and Tyler and Melander (2013) affirm this relationship by showing how children from broken homes are more likely to experience sexual victimisation, violence and drug dependency on the streets.

Furthermore, the movement of families or children from rural to urban areas in search of better economic opportunities, when unplanned, often results in homelessness and informal settlements. Children from such backgrounds, now residing in slums or city streets, are more likely to be trafficked, abused, or drawn into criminal networks. This rural-urban drift without a support structure, as demonstrated by Stephen and Udisi (2016), highlights how internal migration in Nigeria inadvertently contributes to the expansion of the street child population.

Another troubling finding is the cultural stigma associated with witchcraft accusations. In many communities, children perceived as witches are subjected to rejection, torture and expulsion from their homes. This practice, rooted in superstition and reinforced by some religious ideologies, strips children of familial protection and social belonging. Asangausung *et al.* (2025) showed that children accused of witchcraft in Akwa Ibom State were often left to survive on the streets, where they are traumatised and increasingly vulnerable to delinquent behaviour and criminal exploitation. Cultural beliefs of this nature not only violate children's rights but institutionalise abuse under the guise of tradition.

The lack of access to education remains a critical contributing factor to vulnerability. Education is not only a fundamental right but also a protective factor against exploitation and abuse. When children are unable to attend school—whether due to poverty, stigma, or displacement—they are denied not just literacy and skills, but also a safe environment and social integration. Aransiola (2013) noted that children who are out of school often remain idle or are pushed into informal work, further entrenching them in cycles of deprivation and

exposure to danger.

Finally, the failure of institutional frameworks to protect children plays a decisive role in prolonging their suffering. Although Nigeria has adopted the Child Rights Act, its enforcement remains weak in many states. Institutions that should provide support, including child welfare services and law enforcement, are often under-resourced or indifferent. The inability to report abuse, seek justice, or access rehabilitation services means that most of these children continue to suffer in silence. Singh (2016) and Ifayomi *et al.* (2023) have both identified this systemic failure as a major obstacle to addressing child abuse in Nigeria.

In sum, the socio-economic conditions that contribute to the abuse and vulnerability of street children in Nigeria are multifaceted and mutually reinforcing. These include household poverty, parental unemployment, family disintegration, rural-urban migration, cultural superstitions such as witchcraft accusations, lack of access to education and weak institutional protection. As supported by relevant literature, these conditions not only expose children to immediate harm but also entrench them in long-term cycles of deprivation, criminality and social exclusion. Addressing these challenges requires holistic, multi-sectoral interventions that target poverty alleviation, cultural reorientation, educational access, family support systems and robust child protection mechanisms.

What are the manifestations of abuse experienced by street children in Nigeria?

Table 2: Manifestations of Abuse Experienced by Street Children in Nigeria

Type of Abuse	Description	Observed Manifestations	Impacted Domains	Supporting Evidence (Secondary Data)
Physical Abuse	The use of force that causes bodily harm or injury	Bruises, untreated wounds, fractures; beating by law enforcement, older street gangs	Physical health; personal safety	Stephen and Udisi (2016); Asangaung (2024); Singh (2016)
Sexual Abuse	Involvement of a child in sexual activity against their will	Rape, coercive sex, transactional sex for food or shelter; early pregnancy in girls	Reproductive health; emotional stability	Chimdessa and Cheire (2018); Ifayomi <i>et al.</i> (2023); Singh (2016)
Emotional/Psychological Abuse	Persistent exposure to fear, humiliation, or neglect	Depression, anxiety, withdrawal, suicidal tendencies, substance abuse	Mental health; cognitive development	Ogunkan <i>et al.</i> (2024); Asangaung, Okorie, Udousoro and Yagci (2025)

Economic Exploitation	Use of children for labour or financial gain without fair compensation	Street hawking, begging, or working under debt bondage; theft syndicate involvement	Economic autonomy; education	Adewumi and Bwowe (2024).
Neglect	Failure to provide basic needs like food, shelter, or healthcare	Malnutrition, poor hygiene, untreated illness, lack of access to clean water or sleep spaces	Physical health; survival capacity	Cumber & Tsoka-Gwegweni(2015)
Social Abuse	Discrimination, rejection and social exclusion due to child's street status	Stigmatisation, denied access to religious or public services, distrust from community	Social integration; self-worth	Stephen and Udisi (2016); Asangausung, Okorie and Ukommi (2025)
Legal/Institutional Abuse	Harsh or arbitrary treatment by police or legal authorities	Arbitrary arrests, detention without trial, police extortion or harassment	Legal protection; rights enforcement	Akintayo, T. (2021); Singh (2016)

Source: Compiled by the Authors (2025)

The manifestations of abuse experienced by street children in Nigeria are diverse and deeply interconnected, reflecting the severe socio-legal and psychological challenges that confront this vulnerable population. Physical abuse is one of the most overt forms of harm and is commonly inflicted through beatings, assaults, and violent confrontations, particularly with law enforcement officers or older, dominant street gangs. This form of abuse often results in visible injuries such as bruises, fractures, and untreated wounds, which compromise the physical safety and well-being of the children. Studies such as those by Stephen and Udisi (2016) and Singh (2016) have documented numerous instances of such violence, especially in urban environments where children face aggression both from the public and state actors.

Sexual abuse constitutes another major violation. Street children, especially girls, often experience coercive sex, rape and transactional sex as a survival strategy to obtain food, shelter, or protection. The consequences are far-reaching, encompassing reproductive health challenges such as early pregnancies, sexually transmitted infections (STIs) and severe emotional trauma. Chimdessa and Cheire (2018), Ifayomi *et al.* (2023) and Singh (2016) have highlighted the normalization of such abuses, often occurring in contexts where there are no guardians, legal protections, or support systems in place.

Emotional and psychological abuse is also widespread and is reflected in persistent exposure to neglect, fear, and humiliation. These children frequently suffer from depression, anxiety, low self-esteem, and in extreme cases, suicidal ideation or behaviour. The psychological toll is compounded by substance abuse, which many use as a coping

mechanism to escape the emotional strain of street life. Ogunkan *et al.* (2024) and Asangausung *et al.* (2025) both emphasise that emotional abuse, though less visible than physical abuse, has long-term implications on cognitive development and emotional regulation, making rehabilitation more complex.

Economic exploitation is another critical form of abuse. Street children are often used for cheap or unpaid labour, with many forced into hawking, begging, or criminal activities such as pickpocketing or serving as errand runners for gangs. These forms of exploitation deprive them of education and legitimate economic opportunities, thereby reinforcing cycles of poverty and dependency. Adewumi and Bwowe (2024) observe that such children are not only financially exploited but also exposed to further physical and emotional abuse in the process.

Neglect, while often passive, manifests through chronic deprivation of basic needs such as food, shelter, healthcare, and safety. This leads to malnutrition, untreated illnesses, poor hygiene and chronic fatigue. Cumber and Tsoka-Gwegweni (2015) underscore that neglect has become systemic, where institutions and caregivers alike fail to uphold the minimal obligations needed to ensure the children's survival and dignity.

Social abuse, meanwhile, takes the form of persistent stigma, discrimination and exclusion from communal, religious and public services. Due to their perceived deviance or presumed criminality, street children are often denied access to safe spaces, educational opportunities and healthcare. Stephen and Udisi (2016) and Asangausung, Okorie and Ukommi (2025) reveal that such marginalisation contributes to a growing sense of alienation and reinforces their invisibility in both public discourse and policy intervention.

Finally, legal or institutional abuse is a manifestation of systemic failure. Rather than being protected, many street children are subjected to arbitrary arrests, harassment, extortion and unlawful detention by security forces. These abuses highlight the paradox where state institutions, instead of acting as custodians of child welfare, become perpetrators of injustice. As Akintayo (2021) and Singh (2016) illustrate, this legal hostility undermines any confidence the children might have in institutional justice and further entrenches their vulnerability.

Collectively, these manifestations point to a multidimensional crisis where abuse is not only physical but structural, economic and psychosocial. They demand a coordinated response that combines legal reform, poverty alleviation, community sensitisation and targeted rehabilitation to safeguard the rights and dignity of street children in Nigeria.

What are the social, psychological and developmental implications of abuse on street children in Nigeria?

Table 3: Social, Psychological and Developmental Implications of Abuse on Street Children in Nigeria

Dimension	Implication	Manifested Outcomes	Long-Term Risks	Supporting Evidence (Secondary Data)
Social	Social alienation and marginalisation	Stigmatisation, exclusion from schools and places of worship, mistrust of adults	Chronic social detachment, integration failure	Asangausung, Okorie, Udousoro and Yagci (2025); Singh (2016)

	Involvement in deviant peer networks	Gang membership, substance abuse, petty crime	Juvenile delinquency, future incarceration	Ogunkan <i>et al.</i> (2024); Cumber & Tsoka-Gwegweni (2015); Asangausung, Okorie and Ukommi (2025)
Psychological	Emotional trauma and instability	Anxiety, depression, suicidal thoughts, emotional withdrawal	Mental illness, poor emotional regulation in adulthood	Obimakinde and Shabir (2023); Cumber & Tsoka-Gwegweni (2015)
	Identity distortion and self-worth erosion	Low self-esteem, feelings of worthlessness, self-harm	Loss of motivation, future relationship dysfunction	Chimdessa and Cheire (2018)
Developmental (Cognitive)	Disruption in formal education and learning processes	Poor literacy and numeracy skills, frequent school dropout	Lifelong illiteracy, limited employment opportunities	Ogunkan <i>et al.</i> (2023)
Developmental (Physical)	Malnutrition and delayed physical growth due to neglect and abuse	Stunted growth, weakened immune system, poor physical fitness	Chronic illness, impaired physical development	Aransiola (2013); Cumber & Tsoka-Gwegweni (2015)
Developmental (Moral)	Absence of structured moral socialisation	Justification of violence, dishonesty, survival-based ethics	Value disorientation, moral disconnect from society	Ifayomi <i>et al.</i> (2023); Stephen and Udisi (2016)

Source: Compiled by the Authors (2025)

The social, psychological and developmental implications of abuse on street children in Nigeria are deeply interwoven, producing multi-layered and long-term consequences that extend beyond childhood into adulthood. Socially, the abuse and neglect experienced by these children often result in profound alienation and marginalisation. Stigmatised by the public, distrusted by adults and often excluded from schools, religious institutions and public spaces, these children experience a breakdown of social integration. As highlighted by Asangausung, Okorie, Udousoro and Yagci (2025), as well as Singh (2016), this marginalisation breeds chronic detachment from societal norms and values, making reintegration efforts extremely challenging.

In response to such exclusion, many street children gravitate toward deviant peer groups or gangs as a substitute for familial and social support. This social misalignment facilitates involvement in petty crime, drug abuse and other delinquent behaviours. Studies such as those by Ogunkan *et al.* (2024), Cumber and Tsoka-Gwegweni (2015) and Asangausung, Okorie and Ukommi (2025) confirm that exposure to such environments increases the likelihood of future incarceration and entrenched criminal patterns.

Psychologically, the constant exposure to abuse fosters deep emotional trauma. Symptoms such as anxiety, depression and suicidal ideation are common, reflecting a fragile and often deteriorating mental health condition. Obimakinde and Shabir (2023) as well as Cumber and Tsoka-Gwegweni (2015) note that many of these children develop maladaptive coping mechanisms like emotional withdrawal or substance use, which often persist into adulthood as unresolved trauma. Chimdessa and Cheire (2018) further illustrate that prolonged abuse distorts children's self-perception and erodes their self-worth, often leading to self-harm, identity confusion and a disconnection from any aspirational goals.

From a developmental perspective, the consequences are equally severe. Cognitively, most street children experience disruptions in their education due to instability, lack of access, or economic survival pressures. As Ogunkan *et al.* (2023) explain, this results in poor literacy and numeracy skills, frequent dropout rates and limited future employability, thereby reinforcing the cycle of poverty. Physically, malnutrition, poor hygiene, and lack of medical care—common in the street environment—contribute to stunted growth, weakened immunity and poor overall health. Cumber and Tsoka-Gwegweni (2015) and Aransiola (2013) emphasise that these physical deficits can persist into adulthood, affecting productivity and life expectancy.

Equally important is the moral and ethical development of these children. The absence of stable adult guidance and structured moral education creates a vacuum filled by survival-based ethics. Many children grow up normalising violence, deceit and lawlessness as acceptable tools for survival. Ifayomi *et al.* (2023) and Stephen and Udisi (2016) point out that this disorientation results in value disconnect and weak moral grounding, which not only affects their personal development but also poses broader risks to social cohesion and lawfulness in society.

In sum, abuse profoundly undermines the holistic development of street children in Nigeria. The implications stretch across social rejection, psychological instability, educational disruption, physical degradation and moral ambiguity. These findings underscore the urgent need for a coordinated response involving child protection services, mental health interventions, inclusive education policies and community reintegration frameworks that recognise the multi-dimensional nature of street children's experiences.

Conclusion

This study explored the socio-economic conditions that contribute to the abuse and vulnerability of street children in Nigeria, the manifestations of abuse they experience and the social, psychological and developmental implications of such abuse. The findings reveal that household poverty, parental unemployment, family disintegration, rural-urban migration, harmful cultural beliefs such as child witchcraft accusations and weak institutional protection are key drivers pushing children to the streets. On the streets, these children are exposed to a wide spectrum of abuse—physical, sexual, emotional, economic, social and legal. These abuses severely impact their physical health, mental well-being, social integration, cognitive development and moral orientation.

The implications of these findings are significant. Socially, street children face exclusion, stigmatisation and integration challenges. Psychologically, they suffer emotional trauma, identity crises and mental health challenges, while developmentally, they are deprived of educational opportunities, suffer malnutrition and grow with a distorted sense of morality. These conditions not only endanger the immediate well-being of the children but

also pose long-term threats to national development, public health and social cohesion.

Anchored on the thesis that the abuse and vulnerability of street children are products of intersecting socio-economic, cultural and institutional failures, this study contributes to existing knowledge by contextualising the Nigerian street child experience with current empirical evidence and theoretical perspectives. It expands understanding of how systemic neglect and socio-cultural beliefs reinforce childhood marginalisation, while also drawing attention to specific emerging issues in Nigeria, such as parental wiccaphobia, paternity disputes and institutional abuse.

Given these findings, there is a need for urgent policy reform and multi-sectoral intervention. Government agencies, NGOs and community stakeholders should collaborate to strengthen child protection systems, enforce the Child Rights Act, provide access to education and tackle root causes such as poverty, cultural misbeliefs and family breakdown.

Further research should investigate the long-term trajectories of street children who survive abuse, particularly in terms of adult outcomes in mental health, employment and civic engagement. Longitudinal studies would provide a deeper understanding of resilience patterns and help refine rehabilitation frameworks aimed at restoring dignity and opportunity to this vulnerable population.

Recommendations

- i. A comprehensive policy recommendation to address the socio-economic conditions contributing to the abuse and vulnerability of street children in Nigeria is the institutionalisation of a state-level Social Protection and Family Stability Policy. This policy should focus on reducing household poverty, unemployment and family breakdown through coordinated interventions that integrate economic empowerment for vulnerable families, enforce compulsory access to basic education and strengthen the child welfare system. By embedding poverty alleviation, parental support and preventive child protection measures within a single legislative and administrative framework, the state can disrupt the socio-economic pathways that push children onto the streets and expose them to abuse.
- ii. To effectively address the various manifestations of abuse experienced by street children in Nigeria, it is recommended that the state governments formulate and implement a Child Protection and Rights Enforcement Policy that establishes a multi-agency response framework. This policy should prioritise the prevention, identification and response to all forms of child abuse—physical, sexual, emotional, economic and institutional—within both public and informal settings. By mandating specialised child protection units within law enforcement agencies, institutionalising trauma-informed care in shelters and rehabilitation centres and ensuring legal accountability for abuse perpetrators, the policy would create a protective environment that recognises street children as rights-bearing individuals rather than social deviants. Such a rights-based approach would foster systemic change, reduce impunity and promote the social reintegration of vulnerable children.
- iii. To mitigate the social, psychological and developmental implications of abuse on street children in Nigeria, a comprehensive Child Development and Reintegration Policy should be adopted. This policy must be anchored on a rehabilitative and rights-based framework that addresses the long-term consequences of abuse through access

to inclusive education, psychosocial support, health services and structured moral guidance. It should prioritise the reintegration of street children into safe family or community-based environments, while institutionalising state-funded trauma recovery programs and skill-building initiatives that restore the children's social identity, cognitive functioning and moral agency. By framing abused street children as assets for human capital development rather than liabilities, such a policy would promote their full recovery and reintegration into a socially productive life.

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